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DESIGNING WITH USERS: A TEACHING METHOD.

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ABSTRACT

In the last few years the interest towards the study of solutions centered on the human being has grown greatly leading to an ever-increasing cooperation between different disciplines such as sociology, psychology, anthropology, ergonomics, engineering, and medicine which, through Design, finally got in touch.

Transformations affecting economic scenarios on an international level require a prompt update of traditional competitive logics. The nature of innovation changes: the sphere of technologies and forms blends with the sphere of signifiers and experiences.

In relation to such changes, the need for different educational methods and new design ways of expression able to satisfy the extremely interactive potential of new technologies becomes evident. Research and didactic activities will become ever more participatory generating new forms of explorative learning.

This paper introduces the design process used during the workshop in the Final Synthesis Design Studio course at the Politecnico di Milano - Faculty of Design, focused on an explorative learning approach.

Keywords: Creativity, Method, User.

INTRODUCTION

The beginning of the 21st century was marked by an atmosphere of instability and increasing complexity: technological development, the spread of communication networks and major socio-economic turbulences had changed production scenarios and companies' needs. In such context of great transformations of the whole system company-product-market, design becomes an interpreter of

the society and strategic key-point for new production realities. Design needs to assume an ergonomics-oriented approach and a methodology for product innovation where people, both stakeholders and final users, are protagonists of the whole design process. Today, more than ever, the need for a methodological approach able to consider and employ the "creative skills" of the user is evident. The necessity of design approaches able to involve the user both physically and emotionally and evaluate their "creative experience" is emerging. In this perspective, an educational model for design based only on knowledge and the traditional "deductive" method do not seem to meet the needs of new productive assets. It becomes indispensable to approach and investigate "inductive" methods, founded on a more practical know-how, and develop a methodology where to know and to know how, theory and practice, act synergistically. As a matter of fact, the requirements new products need to fulfil do not only revolve around performance, but also include strong social values, innovative materials and technologies and an overall positive impact on the quality of life. Within the horizon of current research in Human-Centered Design, treated thoroughly by E. Sanders of The School of Design at the University of Dundee, the concepts of co-creation and co-design are increasingly predominant within the field of participatory design (Sanders & Chan, 2007). It may be relevant to analyze the connection among creativity, innovation, users and companies (Sanders & Chan, 2007) from what E. Sanders (Sanders, 2006) asserted: "A human-centered design revolution is taking place. Consumerism is no longer enough. The everyday people we serve through design are becoming proactive in their demand for creative ways of living. New design spaces are emerging in

response to people’s needs for creativity. The role of designers will change significantly in the near future”.

CREATIVITY, INNOVATION AND COMPANIES

Creativity is the base for innovation and they have to be considered as complementary activities, there is no innovation without creative ideas. Although often the words creativity and innovation are used interchangeably there are fundamental differences between the two.

This concept is reflected in the widely accepted definition: innovation equals creativity plus implementation (successful).

Innovation enables companies to be competitive, but is not enough to fuel the industrial engine; innovation has to be in the right dose and at the right moment. Therefore, to understand how the creative process generates innovation, it is necessary to understand why innovation is needed and how it is related not only to creativity, but also to companies and design.

Creativity and design are in relation to innovation as the first contributes to the development of available ideas and the second to increase the chance of successfully commercializing these ideas.

Swann and Birke (2005) classified three different models connecting creativity and design to innovation (see Figure 1). In the linear model creativity has a positive effect on Research & Development and consequently a positive effect on innovation (see linear model in Figure 1). Then it is interesting to observe how in the interactive model not only the relations between the different elements of the linear model are considered (see interactive model in Figure 1) but also the importance of design is emphasized. Creativity is linked directly with design and design with innovation. In the third model (see model with creative culture in Figure 1) creative climate takes a central position and relates with all the other elements.

The model represented by Swann and Birke outlines effectively how the introduction of a creative culture in a company may change the interactions between creativity, design and innovation and highlights the importance of a correct management of such processes.

Figure 1 The three model of creativity by Swann and Birke

The European Community lays emphasis on the importance of fostering creative and innovative processes in our societies. In 2009 the European Year of Creativity and Innovation took place (AA.VV, 2009). It was focused on raising awareness on the importance of creativity and innovation as key drivers of personal, social and economic development. The aim of the Year was to promote creative and innovative approaches in different sectors.

Innovation and knowledge economy, the transition towards a creative economy, education for creativity

and innovation, creative ideas and innovative solutions are arising as crucial factors to rescue Europe from the current economic crisis.

"CREATE - Creative Processes for Enterprise Innovation" (2009), focused on companies' ability to be creative, is only one of the many important initiatives supported by the European Union. The aim was to invest in the development of creative abilities with the use of methods and techniques to promote creative environments and, therefore, innovation. Creative thinking consists in facing problems from a basis of solid knowledge, and yet adopting new perspectives, with the aim to find innovative and effective solutions for any purpose.

Creativity is often considered an innate capacity belonging only to a few gifted people, but research shows that it is an ability that can be trained and improved. Psychologists Joy Paul Guilford and Edward de Bono divide the ability of thinking in convergent and divergent (Guilford) or vertical and lateral (de Bono 1998) identified by the way they deal with problems. When the aim is to have a truly different and innovative solution it is necessary to change mental patterns, to be able to see things from a different perspective. It is essential to abandon the convergent/vertical thinking, the one based on logical deductions, to enter into the creative lateral thinking.

Scientific research is oriented towards the development of an educational process, to be adopted by companies as well, able to create the conditions for ideas to emerge. There are various methodologies, techniques and tools conceived with the aim of generating creativity, breaking set patterns, stimulating imagination and improve the environment where creative ideas originate and are developed.

Creativity is a mental and individual matter and involves individuals or groups of individuals cooperating with each other. It requires flexibility, specific expertise, talent and motivation.

To address this reflection it is important to point out that creativity can be learned and developed using tested techniques able to stimulate creative abilities. Such techniques enable people to go past their usual analysis behaviour and consider long-range alternatives and improving productivity and work quality.

It is possible to enhance creativity through training the construction and detection of new relations among concepts before apparently unrelated with the consequent result of the creation of new knowledge.

USER-CENTERED INNOVATION

In the discussion about the competitiveness of the European economic system there is a general agreement about the importance of innovation. The importance of social issues becomes important to strengthen the competitiveness of the European economy. (European Commission 2006).

In the Commission Staff Working Document, "Design as a driver of user-centered innovation" the strong relationship between the use of design and the national competitiveness is underlined.

Nowadays, the meaning of innovation has changed. The sphere of technology and forms merges with that of meanings and experiences. Until now the relation between the physical shape and the function has ruled the theory and the practice of design, while the last decade has seen a permutation towards the user and the user-experience. The expression Human-Centered approach collects all the entries that identify similar research interests, centered on the human being, and it represents the contemporary design approach mostly focused on the user experience.

The design has the task to interpret and reinvent lifestyles and patterns of growth. New technologies will enable the development of radical innovations through services, and personalized and context-based systems.

This dynamic change is not achievable through an incremental innovation, but only through a profound structural change: a radical innovation. Rethinking and reinventing some of the basic social sectors such as health care, education, transport, and overall lifestyles become the only ways of facing the future. The transition from a market-oriented approach to a social-oriented approach (based on research and social innovation) and the use of co-creation methods with stakeholders/users allows the design to respond in an innovative and conscious way to people's new demands.

It seems that this new approach to design is starting to be recognized, accepted and widely available all over Europe. In fact, as a very explicit quote says: «Design for user-centered innovation is the activity of conceiving and developing a plan for a new or significantly improved product, service or system that ensures the best interface with user needs, aspirations and abilities, and allows for aspects of economic, social and environmental sustainability to be taken into account» (European Commission 2009). From the chart proposed it is possible to appreciate how an adequate creative environment is of crucial importance to ensure a satisfactory interaction between creativity, innovation and design.

Figure 2 Measuring system for creativity and innovation based on the European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS).

Hollanders and van Cruysen's model (2009), proposing a measuring system for creativity and innovation based on the European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS), highlights the relevance of the role of education.

New design methods should be structured on experiential aspects coming from the user/product interaction and should include cognitive, emotional and physical aspects. Starting from such assumptions it is possible to refer to an evolved concept of design seen as a strategic chance for companies to generate innovation. We are moving from a design for the user to a design with the user, the so-called participatory design (or co-design), where the involvement of the user becomes a relevant and integral part of the design process.

ACTIVE CREATIVE TRAINING

It is evident today, more than ever, the need for a methodological approach able to consider the context of use and users' "creative abilities". Simple

exercises enabling students to build their own tools and involve the user during the creative phase may strengthen the understanding of delineating new design strategies. From an educational perspective, the main aim is to teach a method to be used in the different design phases, able to help a young designer to understand people's needs and desires not only considering the concrete and cognitive level, but also the emotional.

"Designing for People", and the concept of active involvement of the user, defined in the traditional approach of User Centered Design, is in contrast to the definition of "Designing with People" where the proactive participation of the user is the main focus of attention. The international scientific community identifies the fundamental difference between the two types of research within design, in the way that design with the user necessitates the employment of tools created by the designer with the purpose to stimulate, identify and select ideas generated by "non-designers". This is, for young designers, a key point to be understood and get familiar with as it enables a radical change in the approach to design and its users.

A product to be able to interpret and meet the needs of people's psychological and perceptive spheres, is linked to different factors such as: expectations, desires and aesthetics as separate from social, cultural and generational references. These constitute a research area particularly relevant to design and which identifies new values for the design of everyday objects, a clear evolution from a business model driven exclusively by market needs to a design-driven one (Nussbaum 2004). In Italy, at present, strategies adopted by design-driven companies do not rely on the user involvement as a proactive design resource. It is in such context that it becomes extremely important to form young designers with an understanding of the value of this user approach and it is the aim of the described didactic method to do so.

In connection with the foregoing, a young designer with the ability to handle specific tools and techniques aimed at stimulating new ideas and group problem solving may contribute positively to the competitiveness of any company. Understanding a structured design process is essential for a young designer's ability to master innovative tools,

methodologies and determine the interaction between user and product in designs with such features as: strong social value, innovative materials and technologies and a remarkable impact on the quality of life.

The educational model presented in this paper combines theoretical-conceptual and practical/applicatory aspects with user experiential aspects and results really effective in shaping both instrumental and methodological knowledge necessary to satisfy the profile of a Design bachelor student.

It is interesting to observe how definitions given within design during the last ten years tend to include not only products but also processes and services. Users are considered in a more sustainable perspective and the detection and solution of important social needs may not be necessarily objectified in a physical product, but in a process or a service.

Clearly this reflects the profound and rapid social and cultural changes of our time characterized by a huge technological boost and highly perceptible social needs.

One of the definitions that better represent the concept of proactive design considered in this paper is the one given by the ICSID (The International Council of Societies of Industrial Design) (2008) who defines design as:

“a creative activity whose aim is to establish the multi-faceted qualities of objects, processes, services and their systems in whole life cycles. Therefore, design is the central factor of innovative humanization of technologies and the crucial factor of cultural and economic exchange”.

The understanding of the dynamics underlying the definition of design opens up to the reflection on the importance of identifying adequate educational approaches enabling young designers to handle innovation.

We describe the educational model and the didactic experimentation conducted on the involvement of the user in the design process at the Politecnico of Milan during the Final Synthesis Design Studio course, and document the interesting results of this experience. For students attending the FSDDS as the

final course of their three years educational path it is strategically important to understand the scenarios of the corporate reality they are about to fit into. Traditional market logics need to be rethought and it would be extremely important for a young designer to contribute to the reconfiguration of the relation product/user according to the needs of ever more fluid and flexible markets and societies. The choice for the didactic experimentation requires the introduction of tools created and adopted by important design studios and research groups and the practical experimentation through short exercises of the simplest approaches.

A classroom workshop allowed the students to build up their own work instruments: a set of tools meant to support and stimulate the brainstorm phase. The material assembled during the experimentation was devoted to knowledge elicitation and creativity techniques. It is important to underline how the multidisciplinary approach of this innovative educational model leads the student to a more “conscious” understanding of the whole design process, not limited to creative aspects, but extended to technical, ergonomical and strategic (etc) aspects as well, enabling the student to deal with the actual world of production.

The achieved results will be analyzed referring to case studies of products and product systems developed by the students of the FSDDS using the mentioned innovative educational method.

IDEACTIVITY: A META-METHODOLOGY

For the students attending the Final Synthesis Design Studio course (FSDDS) as the last phase of their Bachelor educational path at the Design Faculty of the Politecnico di Milano, it is strategically important to understand the scenarios and the environment of the business market they are about to enter. Traditional market logics, where design is considered only for its aesthetic value or as an accessory to the final product and not as a business strategy, need to be rethought. It is extremely important for a young designer to contribute to the reconfiguration of the relation product/user according to the needs of the ever more fluid and flexible markets and societies. Identifying needs, desires, behaviours and user's experiences are crucial elements for developing high quality products and services.

Due to the tangible importance of the understanding, handling and developing of tools able to highlight creative aspects arising from people's experiences, part of the lectures held during the FSDS course are dedicated to the introduction of new methods of investigation and new tools.

The FSDS uses an innovative educational model for design: during the course, the knowledge and experience of the professors become part of the student's hands-on designing.

The course is structured in three main stages:

1. Analysis: developing a research focused on defining the brief and the design requirements;
2. Concept: the design goals start "coming to life" in the new ideas: the concepts;
3. Final project: the concepts are developed into an executive standard, bearing in mind the technical and production constraints.

The educational model uses three different didactic modules:

1. Theoretical/methodological lectures given by each teacher of the laboratory in accordance with his field of expertise and scheduled to be an integral part of specific moments of the process;
2. Seminars with professionals held by companies or experts with multidisciplinary skills, in order to provide students with a wider view of the design issues;
3. Tutoring activities: revisions of the projects.

While students work in the classroom the teachers and tutors help them develop their design process via systematic revisions. This is the most important module and it is when learning becomes practice. The students' design process is not linear, it is meant to give the students the incentive to expand and question their work. Thus, the model is iterative and not just consecutive. The development of each project builds up on the student experiments and is examined and fine-tuned according to the personal learning level and the ability to focus on specific issues.

Due to the tendency of research and education of being ever more involving and aimed at generating explorative learning, the research team of the Politecnico, decided to convert a meta-methodology used during creative sessions organized for external companies into an educational method possible to be taught to students and applied to companies.

The aim of the method is to stimulate the students' creativity by working on analogies and brainstorming techniques.

The didactic approach takes the definition of creativity mentioned previously along with the valorisation of lateral thinking followed by a description of the tools associated with the different phases of the design process.

COLLABORATIVE DESIGN TOOLS

User involvement seems to be an emerging attitude, a new way to consider the user a part of the project; it is a basic requirement to develop solutions able to meet the desires of the user. It is necessary for the user to be actively and constantly involved in all of the research phases. The constant and active user participation aims at evaluating the interaction between user and product and interpreting the emotional and physiological responses.

In this method, defined as participatory design or co-design the final users are involved in a direct and proactive way in the design process, they are not only the targets for the final product, but they become part of the creative development of the product itself.

People have to interface with situations and describe them, trying to focus on the process, interact with objects, make some actions and gestures and share and discuss the experience with the designers pointing out obstacles and limitations met in relation to an object or a gesture.

Participatory design techniques are becoming tools highly used in the design of new products and considering this methodology at an early phase of the research is crucial. Teaching this kind of approach that relies on the complete involvement of the user in all the design phases, it is not exclusively a theoretical exercise, but a new way of thinking and acting able to change the roles in the design process.

The research team adopted a process, easy to use and able to support the development of creative and innovative abilities within a company. The approach to the matter was extremely pragmatic in order to demonstrate that each step can be employed. Often due to a lack of internal expertise, companies understanding the potential of creative processes as precursors to innovation, entrust external experts

the task of handling creativity and innovation. Therefore it often becomes necessary for companies to involve external resources to ease design activities.

IDEACTIVITY is a meta-methodology developed on the former considerations with the aim of being a fluid and flexible working tool able to meet the needs of companies with different targets and configurations. With IDEACTIVITY we aspire to elaborate a structured system able to integrate and mix several known techniques. The method depends on the indispensable part of “play”: get involved, collaborate, work as a team towards a common goal and look at things from a different perspective inspired by the others.

IDEACTIVITY is structured in 5 macro-steps, it includes the whole process of generation of a concept:

1_Fact finding and Set up

- Goals, brief analysis and configuration of working teams
- Selection of working approach
- Define groups for creative sessions

2_Creative sessions

- Set up creative sessions and production of working tools
- Idea generation sessions

3_Idea selection and validation

- Analysis and ranking of generated ideas
- Selection of ideas to be developed

4_Firsts concept design

- Synthesis on creative activity

5_Ideas experimental investigation

- Tests on ergonomic, psycho-perceptive and functional features

The paper will go through only the first 2 macro-steps of the method due to their relevance in the educational method proposed.

1_Fact finding and Set up

The first step gives the skills to structure the preliminary research (analysis of the context, historical references, benchmarking, state of art, materials and technologies) as well as the user analysis (target users, conditions of use and possible competitors). It also involves user groups via interviews, questionnaires, direct observations, etc. This phase is important to highlight both the existing issues as well as the specific aims of the final product. It should be noted that in the UCD approach the user is considered in a broader sense, and not only the final consumer, but also every other figure involved during the whole product life cycle. Students are encouraged to carry out trials with users and compare a range of products, similar to the one to be redesigned or reinvented. The idea is to involve users from different backgrounds in a typical environment of use of the product in order to highlight possible design directions.

Interviewed users are not usually involved in the concept and design phases due to didactic timing, but are involved in the final phase of product development, when usability is tested using mock-ups. This step is useful to make the last changes to the product. It allows students to learn the differences between the ideal model of the designer and the model for the user.

At the same time there is the Teaming hypothesis: selection and grouping of people with different competences used to work together and in multidisciplinary contexts.

In a real context the working group would be composed by stakeholders, interdisciplinary experts, people with specific expertise and users while, obviously, some of the mentioned group players can not be present in the didactic simulation. Finally the approach to the creative sessions to be undertaken is defined: number of sessions and participants for each one, management and correlation between the sessions.

try and identify with people and evaluate suggestions or possible design directions. Students are asked to produce at least one for each kind and encouraged to make some more for Try.

Understanding the difference between the cards Ask, Learn, Look and Try is often complex but essential for the achievement of satisfactory results during the creative session. In TRY, for example, in order to be able to appreciate possible suggestions from the user, it is necessary to stimulate situations and interactions using uncommon objects. In LOOK, instead, to observe the user's habitual behaviour, we could ask to try to do something using the method he considers more appropriate. To give the users a series of devices with different features, invite them to choose one and motivate such a choice, despite the use of physical objects, is an ASK as it is a direct request requiring a direct answer.

LEARN card is where the user is expected to show the designer a known information or task and analyze it.

To describe their educational value of the method will follow some examples of cards developed by the students during the class workshop.

The result was unique and educationally stimulating. In the following pictures it is possible to see the development from ideation to production of some cards.

Figure 5 Preliminary sketch for the design of a Look card. The purpose is to observe users while using a glucometer without the support of a solid surface (by A. Appiani).

In figure 5 and 6 are some preliminary sketches and their development, for cards to be used during the creative session with the colleagues acting as users. The ideas described in these cards originate from a technique of image association to discover information about cognitive aspects of the user. The cards are built on a hypothesis based on previously gathered information related to the design to be developed. Each card should have a short text explaining How and Why as well as an evocative image.

The cards can be used to identify specific characteristics for the product and to refine some of the earlier design choices. For example, the card Learn of the design team for a deep fryer shows a visual approach to the selection of the functions that should necessarily be preserved in the product, by providing a selection of images to be ordered by relevance.

Figure 6 Sketches for Learn and Try cards (left) and their final images. The purpose is to observe users simulating disabilities. (by E. Bertolini).

Figure 7 Cards Learn and Try for the design of a deep fryer. It is shown the use of different objects to remove chips from the hipotetic hot oil in the container. (by Lolacono, Mareddu, Miraldi, Molana).

The same team also decided to simulate the immersion of food to be fried using small containers full of water where the “users” had to dip frozen potatoes using the material made available by the design team (nets, skewers, wooden spoons, etc).

Figure 8 Graphic material for quick evaluation of users' favorite food.

It is necessary to have all the material to be used during the creative session ready before starting the

activity. The aim is to enable the participants to visualize their ideas using a practical approach.

Figure 9 Students using foam shapes during a creative session.

Shapes made out of foam or other materials can be helpful to understand product gestualities and detect unusual gestures connected to products with specific features.

Figure 10 Different materials to understand product gestualities.

Idea generation session

From the experience of teaching as part of the FSDS team emerged the tendency of students to become stuck on information gathering (group phase), rather than proceeding to the phase of solution generation. Groups, indeed, are an excellent opportunity to generate creativity since the creative process, supported by a “collective brain”, is faster. As claimed by psychologist K. Lewin, the group is something more than the sum of the singular parts. The brainstorming simulation sees qualitative disadvantages compared to the ideal number of participants and positive attitude.

In this perspective a simulation of brainstorming is carried out. Starting from the meaning of the word brainstorming “brain storm”, the participants are reminded that ideas are generated as a consequence of each other. The starting point would be the design issue followed by a free flow of more or less possible solutions and ideas.

Brainstorming is comprised of two phases: the divergent and the convergent. During the day the students only experience the first one, the divergent phase, in which ideas are produced freely and in big quantity. The person leading the brainstorming session should stimulate the others to propose ideas and write them down using key words. For all creative techniques the following is fundamental: don't make judgments; use analogies and metaphors; invent ideal solutions, starting from imagination goals; link concepts, technologies or objects not previously related; generate a high number of possible solutions.

As in the previous case, the ideation on the card TRY for the design of a juicer, the group decided to use a lateral thinking approach.

Figure 10 Different materials to

During the brainstorming session, they selected various items meant to help extract the juice from

an orange and create a fun atmosphere able to release the flow of ideas spontaneously.

The convergent phase 3, where ideas are selected, evaluated and restricted to a small selection of the most interesting ones, has to consider primarily the identified focus points needed in the final design and then the data coming from users and stakeholders carefully selected and valued in their technical aspects as well. After identifying the satisfactory design solutions there will be their synthesis into the concept.

In these last steps we suggest the importance of the use of traditional techniques such as sketching and preparatory models, in addition to modern representation techniques, technical drawings, 3D modelling, rendering and rapid prototyping that help the designers.

CONCLUSION

The traditional educational method students are exposed to during the first years of their carrier can be described as “from brief to executive design”; it has the aim to go through all the main phases of the design process a designer is supposed to carry out in order to develop a final design proposal from a design brief assigned by a company. The brief and eventual additional requests of the company are the starting point for a variety of design concepts and the following selection of the concept to be developed better responding to the design brief, the philosophy and needs of the company.

This methodology is remarkably different from IDEACTIVITY, developed on User-centered Design, creativity elicitation and user involvement. IDEACTIVITY enables students to perceive the importance of design as a strategic chance for companies to identify and satisfy not only consumers' needs, but also upcoming trends and latent desires.

The IDEACTIVITY model is a very challenging tool for both students and companies. The group multidisciplinary skills, combined with a User-centered Design approach (requiring students to interact directly with the users and get them actively involved) and the students' ability to develop creative instruments to support the design process might become decisive for the economic growth of any company.

As students approaching the FSDS course have no experience of management and stimulation of creativity, the first aim is to show them existing instruments, traditionally used in other disciplines, which can be adapted and turned into new working tools by designers. It is of great importance to make students understand what potential designing a “personal” tool has to stimulate creativity. Some of the positive aspects emerged from the use of IDEACTIVITY with students are:

- learning a method aimed at identifying users’ needs and desires and able to satisfy users on both physical, psycho-cognitive and emotional level.
- understanding and use of an ergonomic-oriented approach to design towards innovation and for wellbeing and safety. Every need identified or expressed by consumers becomes marketing strategy to differentiate the company from its competitors and to offer an added value to users.
- ability to take innovation and creativity as cultural added values in small Italian companies often not able to develop their own design methods.
- understanding of the fundamental importance of an interdisciplinary environment where multidisciplinary skills coexist and cooperate for the final result. Students have the possibility to be confronted with teachers with different fields of expertise and personalities. Therefore students have the opportunity to evaluate the proposed design under different perspectives, take responsibility of their design choices and develop their own personal design approach.

The method was introduced five years ago and the evidence of its results is in the high Bachelor evaluations achieved and in the three patents awarded by projects coming from the FSDS course. Furthermore often companies have shown great interest in developing students’ projects and have taken them into production.

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